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**THE ROLE OF MODERN DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN
PROTECTING THE POPULATION FROM NATURAL DISASTERS AND
EMERGENCIES RELATED TO CLIMATE CHANGE**

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ABSTRACT

It considers the use of modern digital technologies in the prevention, preparation, and elimination of the consequences of emergencies caused by natural disasters and climate change. The article analyzes the significance of innovative solutions such as artificial intelligence (AI), geolocation systems, drones, and sensor monitoring technologies in these processes. In particular, the possibilities of these technologies in real-time assessment of the situation, risk forecasting, prompt notification of the population, and effective organization of search and rescue operations are highlighted. The article also puts forward proposals for the implementation of these technologies in the conditions of Uzbekistan, and substantiates that their practical application will serve to increase public safety.

Keywords: *Emergencies, natural disasters, climate change, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, drones, geolocation, monitoring, population protection.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Рассматривает вопросы использования современных цифровых технологий в предупреждении, подготовке и ликвидации последствий чрезвычайных ситуаций, вызванных стихийными бедствиями и изменением климата. В статье анализируется значение таких инновационных решений, как искусственный интеллект (ИИ), системы геолокации, дроны и технологии сенсорного мониторинга в этих процессах. В частности, освещены возможности данных технологий в оценке ситуации в режиме реального времени, прогнозировании рисков, оперативном оповещении населения и эффективной организации поисково-спасательных работ. Также в статье выдвинуты предложения по внедрению этих технологий в условиях Узбекистана, обосновано, что их практическое применение послужит повышению безопасности населения.

Ключевые слова: *Чрезвычайные ситуации, стихийные бедствия, изменение климата, цифровые технологии, искусственный интеллект, дроны, геолокация, мониторинг, защита населения.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Tabiiy ofatlar va iqlim o'zgarishi natijasida yuzaga keladigan favqulodda vaziyatlarning oldini olish, ularga tayyorgarlik ko'rish va oqibatlarini bartaraf etishda zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish masalalarini ko'rib chiqadi. Maqolada sun'iy intellekt (SI), geolokatsiya tizimlari, dronlar va sensorli monitoring texnologiyalari kabi innovatsion yechimlarning ushbu jarayonlardagi ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Xususan, real vaqt rejimida vaziyatni baholash, xavf-xatarlarni bashorat qilish, aholini tezkor xabardor qilish va qidiruv-qutqaruv ishlarini samarali tashkil etishda ushbu texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlari yoritib berilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada ushbu texnologiyalarni O'zbekiston sharoitida joriy etish bo'yicha takliflar ilgari surilgan bo'lib, ularning amaliyotda qo'llanilishi aholi xavfsizligini oshirishga xizmat qilishi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Favqulodda vaziyatlar, tabiiy ofatlar, iqlim oʻzgarishi, raqamli texnologiyalar, sunʼiy intellekt, dronlar, geolokatsiya, monitoring, aholini himoya qilish.

Input

Today, climate change poses a serious threat to humanity as a global problem. As a result of climate change, natural disasters, including floods, landslides, droughts, and strong winds, are becoming more frequent. These circumstances negatively affect the life and health of the population, as well as economic stability. In addition to traditional approaches, there is a growing need to use modern technologies to reduce these risks and effectively protect the population. Digital technologies can play an important role at all stages of emergency management - prevention, preparation, response, and recovery.

Digital technologies in emergency management

1. Risk forecasting and monitoring are carried out:

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning systems have great potential in predicting natural disasters. They can analyze large amounts of data from climate data, satellite imagery, seismic sensors, and other sources to determine the probability and timing of dangerous events. For example, AI algorithms can predict landslide risk based on soil moisture, precipitation, and terrain data. Sensor monitoring systems monitor the water level in rivers, the temperature in areas with a risk of earthquakes or fires in real time. This information will serve as a basis for emergency services to make operational decisions.

2. Notification and evacuation of the population are carried out:

In emergency situations, prompt and reliable notification of the population is crucial for saving lives. It is possible to distribute risk warnings through mobile applications, SMS messages, and social networks. Location systems are useful in determining evacuation routes, indicating safe locations, and identifying the location

of people in need of assistance. Thanks to these technologies, constant communication between the population and rescuers is ensured, which accelerates response measures.

3. Optimization of search and rescue operations:

Drones have become an indispensable tool in search and rescue operations. They are used to study hazardous areas inaccessible to humans, search for victims, and assess damaged infrastructure. Drones with thermal cameras help identify people in the dark or under the rubble. Robotics can be used to neutralize hazardous materials or conduct inspections in hazardous areas.

Proposals for use in Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan is located in an area with a high risk of climate change and natural disasters, including mudflows, landslides, and earthquakes. Therefore, the implementation of the above-mentioned technologies in our country is of great importance: Creation, jointly with the Ministry of Emergency Situations, of a unified information system based on digital technologies. Installation of automated monitoring stations in mountainous and mudflow-prone areas. Development of a special mobile application that warns the population about dangerous situations. Providing rescue teams with modern drones and geolocation tools. Improvement of the system of training specialists in this area.

Conclusion:

Digital technologies provide new, effective approaches to protecting the population from natural disasters and emergencies related to climate change. The use of artificial intelligence, drones, and geolocation systems serves to save human lives, reduce economic losses, and increase the effectiveness of emergency management. The introduction of these technologies in Uzbekistan will be an important step for the country's security and sustainable development.

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